

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Risk factors for baby blues in postpartum mothers in 2023-2024: A literature review

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Abstract

Introduction: The postpartum period is the period that starts from the first day a mother gives birth to six weeks, or about forty-two days. One type of postpartum depression is baby blues syndrome which is the early stage of postpartum depression and postpartum psychosis. The cause of baby blues syndrome is not yet known for certain, but it is thought to be caused by various factors, including biological changes, stress and social or environmental causes.

Methods: This study used a literature review from systematic search results in the Google Scholar and PubMed databases. The selection of articles was limited to the publication period from 2023 to 2024.

Results and Discussion: From the literature search, there were 6 studies that met the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Among them, 6 studies found a relationship between maternal readiness factors, husband's support, and age with the occurrence of baby blues during the postpartum period.

Conclusion: Maternal readiness in facing childbirth and strong support from the husband are very important factors in preventing baby blues which can affect the well-being of the mother and baby.

Keywords: Baby Blues; Postpartum Period; Risk Factors; Postpartum Mother; Mental Health

1. Introduction

The postpartum period is the period that starts from the first day a mother gives birth to six weeks, or about forty-two days. This is a very important stage for the mother's physical and mental health because she will experience many physical and mental changes during pregnancy and experience a lot of stress during childbirth (1).

According to the Indonesian Health Profile, the number of postpartum mothers in Indonesia in 2019 reached 4,554,868 people (2). The number of postpartum mothers in Indonesia in 2020 reached 4,984,432 people (3). In 2023, the coverage of complete KF visits in Indonesia was 85.7%, where the provinces with the highest coverage were DKI Jakarta Province at 108.9%, Banten at 94.8%, and West Java at 93.8%. The provinces with the lowest coverage included Central Papua (27.7%), Southwest Papua (5.3%) and Papua Mountains (2.6%) (4).

Pregnancy and childbirth are the most important events in a woman's life cycle that can cause great stress (5). One type of postpartum depression is baby blues syndrome, which is the initial stage of postpartum depression and postpartum psychosis. Baby blues syndrome is a form of emotional disturbance due to adjustment to the birth of a baby, which appears from the first day to the fourteenth day after the delivery process, with symptoms peaking on the fifth day (6). Postpartum mothers who experience baby blues syndrome have symptoms including easy crying, sudden changes in feelings, anxiety, excessive worry about the baby, loneliness and decreased sexual desire (7).

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At first glance, baby blues syndrome is not dangerous, but it has a significant impact on child development because mothers with this condition usually cannot care for their children properly, so they cannot provide the nutrition and attention that their children should receive. Mothers are not enthusiastic about breastfeeding their babies, so the baby's cleanliness and development are disrupted. As a result, the growth and development of babies are not the same as babies whose mothers are healthy (8).

Reporting the prevalence of baby blues syndrome varies throughout the world. The prevalence of postpartum depression in the world varies from 6.5% to 15% for 1 year after giving birth (9). The incidence of baby blues syndrome in several countries such as Japan is 15%-50%, the United States 27%, France 31.3% and Greece 44.5%. The prevalence of postpartum depression in developing countries ranges from 2%-74% with the highest prevalence in Turkey (10). The prevalence for Asia is between 26-85% (11).

The cause of baby blues syndrome is not yet known for certain, but is thought to be caused by various factors, including biological changes, stress and social or environmental causes (12). Some factors that may cause baby blues syndrome include the mother's unpreparedness in facing pregnancy and childbirth, lack of support from her husband, unexpected types of childbirth such as cesarean section, lack of knowledge of the mother in breastfeeding and caring for babies and unplanned pregnancies that cause baby blues syndrome (13).

Based on the description above, this study aims to determine what factors are at risk for baby blues in postpartum mothers. The goal is to increase the understanding of health professionals and pregnant women, so that they can anticipate and reduce the risk factors associated with the occurrence of baby blues in the postpartum period. Raising awareness of this condition is essential to reduce its impact on the physical and psychological well-being of pregnant women, as well as ensuring their overall quality of life.

2. Material and methods

This study uses a literature review from the results of a systematic search in the Google Scholar and PubMed databases using the Indonesian keywords "faktor risiko baby blues pada ibu postpartum" and the English "risk factors for baby blues in postpartum mothers". The selection of articles is limited to the publication period from 2023 to 2024. The inclusion criteria selected include open access, full text, having a topic that is in accordance with the research, namely regarding risk factors for baby blues in postpartum mothers. While the exclusion criteria are articles other than research results (original research) such as textbooks on postpartum baby blues, HIV/AIDS risk factors, nursing care reports, and articles discussing infections other than postpartum baby blues. The search results from the keywords entered obtained 917 articles. The next stage was filtering the titles and abstracts so that 15 articles were obtained. After that, articles were selected that were in accordance with the topic regarding risk factors for baby blues in postpartum mothers by reading them thoroughly so that 11 articles remained. Finally, the author selected the most appropriate articles and obtained 6 articles that were selected for research.

3. Results and discussion

Six articles in Indonesian have been reviewed and analyzed as follows.

Table 1 Results of Review of 6 Articles

No.	Author(s)	Title	Edition	Research Method	Results
1	Neti Yuhaeni, Eli Indawati	Analisis Faktor yang Berhubungan dengan Kejadian Baby Blues Syndrom pada Ibu Nifas di Klinik Cempaka Medical Center Tambun Bekasi Tahun 2023	MANUJU: Malahayati Nursing Journal Vol. 6 No. 4 2024	Quantitative analysis with a cross-sectional design	Based on the conducted study, it was found that there is a significant relationship between maternal readiness (p value = 0.006), spousal support (p value = 0.013), delivery type (p value = 0.026), knowledge (p value = 0.006), and pregnancy planning (p value = 0.042) with the occurrence of baby

					blues syndrome in postpartum mothers.
2	Pebrisa Ulfa, Agustina, Mainidar	Analisis Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Terjadinya <i>Baby Blues Syndrome</i> Pada Ibu Nifas di Wilayah Kerja Puskesmas Darul Imarah	Jurnal Promotif Preventif Vol. 7, No. 4 Agustus 2024	Analytical observational using a cross-sectional design.	It was found that age and education are factors associated with the occurrence of baby blues syndrome.
3	Farida Evi1, Anna Waris Nainggolan, Edy Marjuang Purba, Herna Rinayanti Manurung	Faktor-Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Terjadinya <i>Baby Blues</i> Pada Ibu <i>Postpartum</i> di Puskesmas Idi Rayeuk Kabupaten Aceh Timur Tahun 2023	JIMU: Jurnal Ilmiah Multidisipliner Vol. 02, No. 03, 2024	Descriptive correlational with a cross-sectional approach.	Based on the conducted study, it was found that factors such as age, parity, marital status, and readiness influence the occurrence of postpartum blues.
4	Niar, Nur Anita, Nurul Aeni, Nurlina Akbar, Rima Sartika	Faktor yang Berhubungan dengan Risiko Kejadian <i>Post Partum Blues</i>	Jurnal Kesehatan Marendeng: Vol. 8 No.1 (maret, 2024)	Analytical observational with a cross-sectional study design.	Parity (especially primiparity), age, and education are associated with the occurrence of postpartum blues.
5	Anjeli Indah Purwati, Nurhidaya Fitria, Wira Ekdeni Aifa	Faktor-faktor yang Mempengaruhi Kejadian <i>Postpartum Blues</i> di BPM Elizabet Wilayah Kerja Puskesmas Payung Sekaki	Health Care: Jurnal Kesehatan 12 (1) Juni 2023	Observational-analytical using a cross-sectional design.	There is a relationship between age, occupation, family support, and income with the occurrence of postpartum blues.
6	Agus Santi BR Ginting	Faktor-faktor yang Mempengaruhi Kejadian Post Partum Blues di TPMB I Tahun 2024	Journal Of Midwifery Vol. 12 No. 2 Oktober 2024	Cross sectional.	Maternal readiness and spousal support can influence the occurrence of postpartum blues. Spousal support is a significant factor.

Baby blues is an emotional condition commonly experienced by mothers after childbirth, usually characterized by feelings of sadness, anxiety, frequent crying, and sleep disturbances. This condition typically appears within 2 days to 3 weeks after delivery. Several factors influence the occurrence of baby blues, including the mother's physical and psychological readiness, age, parity (number of births), and the social support received, particularly from the husband (14). Mothers who do not adequately prepare themselves, both physically and mentally, are more susceptible to feelings of anxiety and stress, which can trigger the onset of baby blues. Research shows that mothers under the age of 20 or over 35 are at a higher risk of experiencing baby blues. Younger mothers often lack experience in baby care, while older mothers tend to be more anxious, and their physical condition may also decline (15).

In addition to age, parity also plays an important role in the occurrence of baby blues. Primiparous mothers, or those giving birth for the first time, are at a higher risk of experiencing baby blues compared to multiparous mothers, who have more experience in baby care (16). Social support, especially from the husband, has also been shown to play a significant role in preventing the onset of baby blues. A husband who provides emotional and practical support, such as offering attention and helping with baby care, can help the mother feel calmer and reduce postpartum stress. Research shows that mothers who receive good support from their husbands are more likely to avoid baby blues and are better able to cope with postpartum challenges (17).

The mother's preparedness for childbirth also significantly influences the likelihood of experiencing baby blues. Mothers who adequately prepare themselves physically and psychologically, such as by having routine check-ups, taking care of themselves, and obtaining sufficient information about pregnancy and childbirth, are more likely to avoid

baby blues. This preparation helps mothers feel more ready and positive in facing the changes that occur after childbirth (18). Research by Saleha (2021) revealed that mothers who feel unprepared, both physically and psychologically, are more at risk of experiencing baby blues compared to those who have adequately prepared (19).

Overall, these studies indicate that the mother's physical and mental readiness, as well as support from the husband, play key roles in preventing the occurrence of baby blues. Mothers who feel prepared and receive strong support from their husbands are better equipped to face postpartum challenges and are less likely to experience significant emotional disturbances. Therefore, it is crucial for mothers to prepare well before childbirth and ensure they have support from their husbands and families to prevent baby blues, which can affect the well-being of both the mother and the baby (12).

4. Conclusion

Baby blues is an emotional condition commonly experienced by mothers after childbirth, with feelings of sadness, anxiety, and frequent crying often emerging. Several factors influence the occurrence of baby blues, including maternal readiness, spousal support, and age. Mothers who feel unprepared, both physically and psychologically, as well as those who do not receive adequate emotional support from their husbands, are at a higher risk of experiencing baby blues. Conversely, mothers who feel prepared to face the postpartum changes and receive full support from their husbands are more likely to cope with stress better. Therefore, maternal preparedness for childbirth and strong support from the husband are crucial in preventing baby blues, which can affect the well-being of both the mother and the baby.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

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References

- [1] Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia. Let's Routinely Check the Health of Mothers and Babies During Postpartum! [Internet]. [cited 2023 Dec 16]. Available from: <https://ayosehat.kemkes.go.id/yuk-rutin-periksa-kesehatan-ibu-dan-bayi-semasa-nifas>
- [2] Ministry of Health. Indonesian Health Profile 2019. Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia. 2019.
- [3] Ministry of Health. Indonesian Health Profile 2020. Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia. 2020.
- [4] Kunta Wibawa Dasa Nugraha. Indonesian Health Profile 2023 [Internet]. Jakarta: Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia; 2024 [cited 2024 Dec 9]. Available from: <https://kemkes.go.id/id/profil-kesehatan-indonesia-2023>.
- [5] Yuhaeni N, Indawati E. Analysis of Factors Related to the Incidence of Baby Blues Syndrome in Postpartum Mothers at the Cempaka Medical Center Clinic, Tambun, Bekasi in 2023. *Malahayati Nursing Journal*. 2024 Apr 1;6(4):1351-72.
- [6] Diah. Risk Factors Affecting the Incidence of Postpartum Blues. Darul Ulum Islamic Boarding School University, Jombang; 2020.
- [7] Mansur H. *Maternal and Child Psychology for Midwifery*. Salemba Medika; 2022.
- [8] Rahayu S. *Family Nursing*. Graha Ilmu; 2020.
- [9] Misri S, Swift E, Abizadeh J, Shankar R. Overcoming functional impairment in postpartum depressed or anxious women: a pilot trial of desvenlafaxine with flexible dosing. *Sage Journals*. 2016.
- [10] Norhayati MN, Nik Hazlina NH, Aniza AA, Asrenee AR. Severe Maternal Morbidity and Postpartum Depressive Symptomatology: A Prospective Double Cohort Comparison Study. *Research in Nursing & Health*. 2016.
- [11] Miyansaski UM. Comparison of the incidence of postpartum blues in postpartum mothers with normal delivery and cesarean section. 2021.
- [12] Bobak IM, Lowdermilk DL, Jensen MD. *Textbook of Maternity Nursing*. EGC; 2021.
- [13] Sujiyatini. *Obstetric Pathology Care*. Nuha Medika Library; 2021.

- [14] Fira S, Ahmad Hidayat FNA. Factors Affecting the Incidence of Baby Blues in Postpartum Mothers at Dr. H. Moch Ansari Saleh Hospital, Banjarmasin. *Innovative Education Journal*. 2023.
- [15] Aryani R. Factors Related to Baby Blues Syndrome in Postpartum Mothers at Dr. Zainoel Abidin Hospital, Banda Aceh City. 2022.
- [16] Elin NA. The Relationship between Age and Parity to the Incidence of Postpartum Blues in Postpartum Mothers in Sambelia District, East Lombok. 2023.
- [17] Sylvia. Postpartum Depression. Faculty of Health, University of Indonesia; 2021.
- [18] Asih, Y and Risneni. Textbook of Postpartum Midwifery Care and Breastfeeding. Trans Info Media; 2021.
- [19] Saleha S. Midwifery Care during the Postpartum Period. Salemba Medika; 2021.